

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE IMPACT MECHANISM OF CLIMATE CHANGES ON THE HUMAN ORGANISM AND TASKS AHEAD

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Abstract

The article discusses the negative effects of climate change, anthropogenic emissions on global warming, and large-scale changes in weather conditions. Attention is drawn to the global increase in the unprecedented effects of climate change on humanity and the Earth's climate system since the middle of the 20th century. A plan to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 40% by 2050 was put forward at COP 29, which was held in Baku, the capital of Azerbaijan, in November 2024. The fact that more than 90% of the main cause of warming is the emission of carbon dioxide (CO₂) and methane, greenhouse gases, is one of the actual problems of the article. Although the main source of emissions is the burning of natural fuel (coal, naphtha and gas) for energy consumption, the article also discusses the need to solve the problem of land conservation, cutting down trees, and the fact that industrial processes also play a major role, which threatens humanity as a serious problem. The purpose of the article is to highlight the urgent issues of taking into account the danger that increased evaporation will lead to stronger storms and extreme weather conditions in the near future, that is, the protection of Planet Earth, the duty of all mankind.

Keywords: COP 29, climate change, global warming, green world.

The motto of the COP 29 event held in Baku, the capital of Azerbaijan, is: United in the name of the Green World

Climate change includes both global warming caused by anthropogenic emissions and resulting large-scale changes in weather conditions. Although climate changes have occurred in previous periods, since the mid - 20th century, humankind has created an unprecedented impact on the Earth's climate system, causing changes on a global scale [3]. The main cause of warming is the emission of greenhouse gases, more than 90% of which are carbon dioxide (CO₂) and methane [4]. Although the main source of these emissions is the burning of natural fuels (coal, naphtha and gas) for energy consumption, land savings, felling of trees and industrial processes also play a role in this [5]. No recognized institution in the national or international arena opposes the human factor in climate change [6]. Reactions to climate change – loss of snow and ice cover that reflect sunlight, increased water vapor (the essence of deposition), and changes in dryness and carbon dioxide in the ocean – increase in temperature It either speeds up or slows down. The increase in temperature in the dryland is approximately twice the global mean increase, which causes the expansion of deserts, the increase of heat waves and oak fires [7]. Increased evaporation leads to stronger storms and extreme weather conditions [8]. Temperature increases occur in the Arctic, causing permafrost to melt, ice caps to retreat, and sea ice to disappear [11]. Additional heat also increases the risk of critical triggering factors [12]. Effects on ecosystems include displacement or extinction of many types of biology as the environment changes – particularly in coral coasts, mountains and the Arctic. [13].

Climate change jeopardizes food shortages and shrinking water supplies, and contributes to economic impulses; It is also thought that it will increase people's displacement from their homeland. Climate change, which the World Health Organization considers to be the greatest threat to global health in the 21st century, also increases the risk of floods, roadborne diseases and extreme heat [14].

Countries from various countries of the world participated in the COP 29 measures held in Azerbaijan on 11-22 November 2024, and fruitful negotiations took place in this field. passes.

The Conference of Parties (COP) of the Framework Convention on Climate Change of the United Nations is held every year. In the name of the world, The Conference of the Parties (COP) aims to achieve consensus on the Paris Charter and Convention and ensure global unification based on the latest technical information and developments by 1.5°C. They are official measures of the Conference of the Parties adopted by governments to limit international relations. In the time of COP measures, world leaders should evaluate their relations and hold discussions on the best ways to deal with climate changes. They come together for this purpose. Currently, the Convention consists of 198 countries (197 countries and the European Alliance). More detailed information about what the COP is, the COP process, the issues discussed and the many multilateral activities that have been implemented can be found in BMT's Climate Changes. It is possible to obtain it from the website of the Framework Convention (UNFCCC) (18; 19; 20).

Although efforts to minimize future sea leveling are beneficial, there are a number of impacts, including rising sea levels, stabilization of ocean temperatures, and ocean acidification. It will continue for centuries

[15]. Most of these effects are now felt at the stabilization level, which is currently around 1.1 °C (2.0 °F) [16]. Since climate change has increased by 1.5 °C (2.7 °F) and continues to rise further, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) has determined that significant increases in these effects have been published. He published a number of accounts showing that he was prognosed [16]. It is possible to respond to climate change through mitigation and adaptation. When it comes to mitigation, the reduction of gas emissions and their removal from the atmosphere are taken into consideration, these methods include the development and effective use of low-carbon energy sources such as wind and solar. These include gradually stopping the use of coal, increasing the efficiency of energy, and maintaining and protecting forests. Adaptation consists of adapting to the actual or anticipated climate through improved coastal protection, better management in times of disasters, and the development of more resilient crops [17]. Adaptation cannot offset the risk of "severe, widespread and irreversible" effects [18]. Essentially, according to the Paris Agreement, the nations agreed to keep their national frontiers "below 2.0 °C (3.6 °F)". Considering these promises, by the end of the century global warming will reach approximately 2.8 °C (5.0 °F) and the current political temperature will be approximately 3.0 °C (5.4 °F). The plan to limit global warming to 1.5 °C (2.7 °F) could be implemented if emissions were halved by 2030 and to zero by 2050.

Climate changes affect not only the surrounding environment but also various aspects of human health, creating a wide range of problems. For example, the increase in temperature, the deterioration of air conditions, the increase in extreme climate events and the change of biological ecosystems directly and indirectly affect human organism. In this article, we will try to investigate these mechanisms with scientific facts and samples. Temperature Increase and Heat Waves are the cause of various phenomena in different parts of the planet.

According to the information of the World Health Organization (WHO), the rise in global temperature in the last ten years has caused the premature death of approximately 150 thousand people every year. Especially during the heat waves that broke out in Europe in 2003, more than 70 people lost their lives in France and Italy. There is a serious need to take care of the health of the population by investigating the principles of its mechanism. Observation and experience have shown that, during periods of heat exposure, hot air makes it difficult for the skin to evaporate from the body. This can result in heat rash and fatal hyperthermia. Those who are most affected by climate problems are the weakest groups - the elderly, the young and those with chronic illnesses. During the 2019 heat wave in India, the temperature reached 50°C and caused hundreds of deaths. Air Pollution and Breathing Problems. Constant carbon emissions and dust storms caused by drought increase the level of pollutants in the atmosphere. According to NASA's research, approximately 7 million people lose their lives every year due to air pollution. Facts show that increased ozone concentration

in urban areas increases the intensity of asthma attacks. For example:

- During the oak fires in 2017 in the USA, the air quality in the city of San Francisco reached 500 AQI (excessively dangerous), which caused the transportation of thousands of people. This led to his application to Xəstəxana.

- Long-term air pollution in China has led to an increase in lung diseases.

The negative effects of extreme climate events on people's psychology should also cause humanity to think.

Climate changes cause disasters such as floods, hurricanes and droughts to occur more frequently. These events affect human health both physically and psychologically. In general, the wars that have broken out in recent years, climate disasters, the removal of chemical weapons from storage, the sending of countless and incalculable rockets in the cosmos, and other secret secrets. Experiments that threaten climate change and human resilience have placed all humanity in danger of extinction. How should we counteract these disasters, what precautions should we take to ensure that living beings and life continue on Planet Earth? Each individual must do their part in this work so that life can continue.

Of course, the increase in the number of injuries and deaths during disasters can also create a stressful situation. There are many reasons why psychological stress and the impulses created by disasters cause long-term depression and trauma in people:

- During Hurricane Katrina in 2005, more than 1,800 people died and more than 1 million people were left homeless. This created mass psychological distress. Food Safety and Malnutrition. Climate changes affect global food production. Changes in rainfall patterns and droughts reduce crop yields and cause food conflicts:

- Due to the drought that broke out in Eastern Africa in 2020, 20 million people in the region suffered from hunger.

- The decrease in wheat crop production led to an increase in global food prices.

- In the Sindh region of Pakistan, land productivity decreased by 30% due to water conflict, which increased malnutrition.

The spread of diseases is another fearful situation. Climate changes expand the range of diseases spread by insects. Especially in hot climates, it affects the environment, causes inflammation and increases the risk of Zika virus. According to research by the World Bank, the areas where some diseases spread to the country may expand by more than 20% by 2050.

- In 2016, the Zika virus epidemic in Brazil was associated with climate changes.

- In the year 2023, balance heat events increased by 40% in Eastern Africa due to the increase in hot air and rainfall.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the effects of climate changes on human organism are wide and varied. Increasing temperature, deteriorating air quality, extreme events, food hazards and the spread of diseases are the main mechanisms of these effects. To counter-

act these processes and reduce health risks, global protections against climate change must be strengthened. Climate change combined with human activity plays a significant role in increasing oak fires and is believed to affect future climate variability in many biomes such as tropical precipitation. It will increase the risk and severity of oak fires. The change of the climate system poses obvious dangers, and many of the changes observed since the 1950s have caused unprecedented changes over the decades. shows. The atmosphere and the ocean warm up, the amount of snow and ice decreases, the sea level rises, and the concentrations of istixana gases increase, etc.

Carbon gas is produced through natural combustion (coal, natural gas and naphtha), solid waste, trees and other biological materials, as well as through certain chemical reactions. As a result, it enters the atmosphere. The use of natural fuels is the main source of CO₂. CO₂ also has direct effects on people's consumption of timber and on other areas where land is used - for example, the breaking of trees, areas for land savings. It can spread through clearing and degrading of soils. During the production and transportation of coal, natural gas and naphtha, methane gas is spread around. Emissions of methane originate both from the decay of individual crops in the wastelands where there are agricultural harvests from livestock and other land-saving areas. Numerous empirical evidence of the unprecedented impact of humans on the Earth System and its global scale (Steffen et al., 2016; Waters et al., 2016) has led many scholars to realize that the Earth is entering a new geological era. He concluded: this era was the Anthropocene. Global consolidation in the last decades has led to the disappearance of ice caps and glaciers, a decrease in the snow cover and the extent and thickness of arctic sea ice, and an increase in the temperature of the cryosphere due to the increase in permafrost temperature. He made it short and removed it. Based on current promises, the world will warm by 2.8°C - close to twice the limit agreed in Paris - by the end of the century. Since the pre-industrial period, the dry air temperature has increased approximately twice from the global average temperature. Climate change has "driven" - we might say with regret - the idea of desertification and land degradation in many regions.

Mountain and arctic ecosystems and biology are particularly sensitive to climate change... As ocean temperatures warm up and the ocean becomes pickier, algae bleaching and coral extinction are likely to increase. "Since climate change is the greatest threat to global resilience in the 21st century, the duty of healthcare workers to present and future generations has become even more fundamental." They protect people from the effects of climate change - warmer weather waves and other extreme weather events; malnutrition; In order to be protected from the effects of environmental pollution, it is possible to prevent damage to the respiratory system, breathing, urinary-vascular and other diseases that are not related to the urinary system. They are on the front lines of treating people who are suffering.

Persistent anthropogenic emissions of SCO₂ and non-CO₂ non-anthropogenic emission forces, which are

decreasing within decades, prevent the rise of the sea level or the climate system. It will underpin anthropogenic global expansion in this period, although it will not underpin many other aspects of its regulation. Persistent anthropogenic emissions of SCO₂ and non-CO₂ non-anthropogenic emission forces, which are decreasing within decades, prevent the rise of the sea level or the climate system. It will underpin anthropogenic global expansion in this period, although it will not underpin many other aspects of its regulation. In model pathways with no or limited overshoot of 1.5°C, global net anthropogenic CO₂ emissions decline by about 45% from 2010 levels by 2030 (40–60% interquartile range), reaching net zero around 2050 (2045–2055 interquartile range). All sectors and societies should take into account the causes and consequences of climate changes and remain concerned about the health of humanity and the planet Earth. Otherwise, this beautiful world of ours is doomed to be destroyed very soon. For example

Azerbaijan's initiatives related to "green" energy: Azerbaijan aims to rise to the top of the most productive countries in the field of energy and benefits from its rich energy and solar potential for this purpose. This is also a key component of the country's plan to reduce decommissioning missions by 40% by 2050. The country aims to improve its current energy system in order to increase the share of electricity generated in electricity generation to 30% by 2030 and become a leader in the field of green energy. Azerbaijan will renew its national goals in accordance with the 1.5°C goal in the future within the framework of the documents defined as an exemplary country in this field.

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